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A Study on Cyber Security from a Safety and Awareness Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Cyber security in India is seeing a sharp incline in both crime and cyber attacks. Therefore, these attacks involve human beings who either directly or indirectly assist the hackers, providing them with an opportunity to readily obtain personal information. Our youth are growing at a rapid pace, and this is a developing nation in comparison to other nations and targeted by hackers from many countries. This paper focuses on an important issue of tracking cyber attacks and protecting our devices from hackers. One of the aims of hackers is to creating security for unauthorized individuals and provides cyber security from cyber hackers. Giving hackers a chance to do their work is a serious crime known as cybercrime. Every online user can avoid these digital crimes by using the CIA TRAIID to maintain cyber security. Advanced technologies will be a safeguard in this digital world. Ransom ware contributes to financial loss but will also help secure spaces with high security. Cyber hackers will pose a serious threat to all Indian forces and is a very critical infrastructure of India.

Keywords:-*Cyber Security, Cyber War, Cyber Attacks, Cyber Crimes, Digital Crime, CIA TRAIID, Digital World, Ransom ware, Indian forces.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Indian nation is capable of developing all devices and maintain a cyber-shield for all networks. The Indian army, navy, air force, NASA, and ISRO are all major players in the country's development. Every force plays a crucial role in the development of nation. The nation is always protected by the four pillars (backbone) as given above. It's time to take responsibility for every person and safeguard our foundations and pillars of nation [1]. The practice of secure online environment will play a pivotal role in securing our nation and in the entire world. In modern era, war among nations is not a physical activity but they are using weapons of new era such as cyber security and hacking. Technology is now developed by combining hardware and software, and everyone's hands are armed with a large weapon known as a mobile phone [2]. Presenting this mobile world, which will be used to create a new war environment called Cyber War. Maintaining cyber security everywhere is the practice of preventing unauthorized individuals from accessing data on computer systems and networks.

Protecting our devices from the entire cyberspace or cyber era is made possible by cyber security. Therefore, in addition to safeguarding our devices, cyber security also protects our personal information (for example, our daily activities in real life will be protected by this cyber-secured space). Recent statistics show that a cyber attack occurs every 39 seconds. Due to an increase in Man of the Middle attacks, there have been a lot of attacks. These days, they also attack small and medium-sized business solutions every 39 seconds, with an average global cost of \$3.9 million for data breaches [5].

In 2018, the total cost of cybercrime committed worldwide exceeded \$1 trillion. Nowadays, cyber attacks cause the most

damage everywhere. The U.S. FBI also reported a 300% increase in cybercrimes since COVID-19 [6]. Additionally, human error accounts for 95% of cyber security breaches. Any unforeseen human error will become vulnerability for cybercriminals. We should use digital devices and the internet with caution and never show your trust in strangers. A variety of technologies and scams are used to trap and hack our data. We should avoid being drawn in by strangers who offer us jobs or free offers of lakhs of dollars just by clicking links. (Unknown calls, scam calls).

Categories of Cyber Attacks:

There are roughly fifty to sixty different kinds of cyber attacks: Some of the most popular attacks are 1. Phishing attack 2. Password Protection 3. Secure Internet 4. Security of emails 5. Malware

1. **Phishing Attack:** A third party is watching you and recording everything you do, including where you are and what you are doing, in order to compile all of our personal data. They collect information just like a example of fish caught by a fishermen. Phishing attackers can be seen hacking our data in your immediate vicinity.
2. **Password Attack:** Many people regularly set their passwords on our devices with the details of date, month, and basic symbols and numbers of birthdates and father and mother names, cell phone numbers, and daily usage of (simple data). Hackers are being given an opportunity by this to readily hack our account using personal information. We should avoid using simple passwords and don't use the same one on multiple devices. Please keep your passwords strong (using letters, numbers, symbols, and special characters) and update them frequently. Each participant keeps our password secure and everybody should assume

that using a simple password will make us weak.

3. **Safe Internet:** Firewalls are a great tool for establishing security. Try to avoid clicking on phony links and unreliable websites and make a regular practice to click on the reliable links and websites. Update your gadgets often and continue using antivirus software to keep your internet safe and secure.
4. **Email Security:** Unauthorized individuals or organizations are sending links in emails to collect our personal information and these people are trying to collect your information for hacking activities. The data hackers collect are like, what data do you regularly search for? Based on that data, these hackers or unauthorized individuals have blackmailed you to demand large sums of money, properties, etc. Additionally, we constantly update our operating system and change our mail passwords. Please use strong passwords and keep them private [9].
5. **Malware:** Malware is causing harm to our network devices. Malware simply displays a message that says, "Click this message." Once you click it, the virus automatically starts functioning properly on all of our devices. Our entire device is automatically infected by this malware. Hackers gradually control our mobile and system from functioning. Stop clicking on any links or messages which is not trust worthy [16].

Anyone who has ever used a laptop, personal computer, or office network device to log in with their email must sign out properly. Once your work is finished, make sure to properly log out of our email. It's known as a lottery scam when someone sends you an email saying, "Congratulations, you won the lottery."

Click on the link, if you follow them then they will take your hard earn money. Hackers also send messages like "Emergency Alert," asking for your password and email address. In a matter of seconds, you are arrested in what is known as a "digital arrest" after a large amount of data or information changes your email address to one from another state. Hackers used these techniques to blackmail people.

- Cyber Crime Against Individuals
- Cyber Crime Against Property
- Cyber Crime Against Organization
- Cyber Crime Against Society

Cybercrime was declared a criminal activity in 2000. A total of 800,000 cyber attacks have been documented in the past, but hackers are constantly improving their methods to cause significant issues for regular people. Hacking has become a threat over the past 21 years. Between 2001 and 2021, 6.5 million victims of cybercrimes experienced this issue. India experienced a high number of cybercrimes following the COVID-19 pandemic, which put everyone in a difficult situation [10]. However, there were 79 million active cyber attacks during that time as well. Hackers launched over 2328 attacks every day on average there is an attack every second.

Cyber Attack resistant Standards

Globally, India currently projects that by 2025, our annual expenses will total \$10.5 trillion. In terms of cyber attacks, India is the second most targeted country in the top ten. CIA TRAIID stands for Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability. The CIA TRAIID is used to identify problem vulnerabilities and develop workable solutions for networked devices and computer systems. In order to maintain better equipment that can easily handle any threats, all of these standards must be met [13].

Confidentiality

The term "confidentiality" describes an organization's efforts to keep our data private. It is restricted to prevent access by unauthorized individuals. This is beneficial because it restricts access to authorized individuals and keeps others out, making it seem secure.

Intentional or human error brought on by negligence or a lack of awareness can also be caused by confidentiality. Maintaining AES (Advanced Encryption standards) will help to protect your data. Use a virtual private network, or VPN, to protect your data so that it moves safely and securely.

Integrity

Integrity offers trustworthy and undistributed data. Only our data is accurate and trustworthy if your data is kept safe. Only authentic, trustworthy, and dependable data should be used when implementing data integrity. Credentials such as passport, driver's license etc will be used to verify your identity.

Availability

Unauthorized users have less access to system application data, when the network is operational for authorized users. Every system has to deal with limited hardware or software level while the system is gradually going down. The data availability is the basic operation for authorized and legal users. This minimizes system halts caused by human error, whether intentional or inadvertent. Updates will be made to servers, network apps, and software on a regular basis for effective data availability. Backup and recovery services will also be provided to ensure secure protection. After witnessing a negative incident, CIA Traid is crucial for determining what went wrong and for assisting with confidentiality and handling ransom ware attacks. However, the system still maintains confidentiality and is readily available to address the week

points that need to be changed in order to use successful security.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to ADITI Singh (2021) [3], the digital age and data are important in our everyday lives. In the online world, our everyday lives become more informative and communicative, and a digital world is created where you can transform it into a technological one. Our sensible data is shared on the intranet [internet] at anytime, anywhere, and cyber eyes are always ready to hack it. Cybercriminals are the main cause of the cyber threat in our nation and the world. Hackers can now access our sensitive data everywhere by using network devices [in our hands]. It's effective to demonstrate how every network device establishes a cyber security safeguard. These days, lot of hackers use cyber threats to steal important documents and evidence. The newest cyber shield technologies can be used to secure our networks. Hacking is a crime, and cyber threats are dangerous [4]. Hacking of network devices is declared as a dangerous and unlawful problem [7]. Professional and international cyber strike analysis is provided by this study in detail [8].

Over the past year, counter measures have been observed globally for reducing the risk of cyber attacks. Furthermore, "ransom ware" is a Russian term for "hacking group" [5]. In July 2021, ransomed ware, also known as an operation, took place as one type of cyber fraud or cheating activity [15]. The specifics of cyber attacks on computer networks are covered in detail in the article [11]. The authors have developed the strategic methods that cybercriminals and cyber vulnerabilities employ [12]. Cyber security is an emerging secure field that is heavily utilized for the recently accessed Internet of Things (IOT) and suggests comprehensive security [18]. Additionally, it lists as an effective solution for DDOs

(Distributed Denial of Service) and malware and phishing. Organizations and individuals are most affected by ransomware and insider threats [19]. Organization failures are occurring due to secure cyber threats that result in financial loss and sensitive data [23].

In IOT 4.0 industry, it is advised to use software and hardware that combines research and enhances cyber defenses against threats to prevent hacking. After that, each employee will receive individualized training and rigorous authentication to raise their awareness of the deeper cyber vulnerabilities on our exhibitions and environment credits [24]. The digital security of today will become the security of tomorrow. In today's society detecting cyber threats is one of the most challenging concepts and providing data security is a big task for everyone. Cyber issues are not a trivial subject. It is challenging to explain what a cyber threat is, who poses a threat, why, and the high frequency of cyber threats. They have shared information on every cyber attack in the past by collecting intelligence reports and conducting cyber monitoring. The significance of cyber safety and data security in ICT (information and communication technology) emergencies in all national infrastructures on cyber security issues can be connected to the social media environment of today. E-Government is working on this project, and e-commerce is also assisting with these cyber issues [25].

Cyber security is crucial for digital protection in the cutting-edge world of businesses, organizations, and innovations. Everyone believes that the new technologies that are currently being developed can have a high security measure. However, nobody is aware that there are popular attacks and that criminal activity is known as cybercrimes can create a disastrous situation. Hackers

gradually warn as a result of the use of cutting-edge technologies to maintain cyber security, and they automatically gain more power and employ new techniques to breach network devices. Network security is a rapidly developing problem in India firmly proclaimed cybercrime to be a criminal offense. Online platforms that create our personnel data while utilizing electronic devices are a prime target for hackers.

In order to get out of the hacking activities, we need to raise awareness among the general public. They begin by raising awareness among students, which will then spread to colleges and schools and eventually reach our parents. Trends in cyber security technology regarding cyber attacks and cybercriminals are presented in this paper, along with information on cyber protection [28]. The air forces today also suffer from a lack of cyber security. Everybody uses computer networks and digital devices, including government agencies, commercial enterprises, and the private sector. Every piece of information is connected to digital devices, including public services like online shopping, transportation, and work-from-home jobs. There are numerous critical cyber threat infrastructures that affect the devices. Because the cyber security benchmarks are not precisely followed, using our own devices at airports is particularly vulnerable to cyber attacks. Additionally, hackers target all airport control systems. Airport control systems are the primary focus of established cyber security standards that are possible to maintain. The best way to overcome this is to raise public awareness and hold mock drills [29]. Cybercriminals utilize the complete passenger data list in these airports, which is very helpful to them. Hackers will then use the passengers' data to blackmail and maintain cyber security standards at National and international airports are essential to the development of our

motherland's economy. In order to develop the best cyber security safeguard, smart airports will be created, and passengers will be asked to review any changes that will be made based on their sensor systems. One of the essential needs of the hour is to maintain strong cyber security in airports without creating any security flaws [30].

In modern technical world, cyber warfare using advanced technologies is a crucial combination of modern war fare that will transform all digital/electronic signals as the part of cyber ware fare [32]. However, online warfare causes the world to be destroyed in ways that are both unexpected and unbelievable. The two nations' armed forces need to spent lot of their efforts to overcome the disruptions caused by the cyber wars. To uphold a set of uniform cyber regulations in order to manage all cyber disruptions, a standard security protocols have to be maintained. The Indian army just finished the war, or Operation Sindhoor, which involved cyber war fare. To defend cyber war fare in India, Ajit Doval sent the crucial information saying, "Another country is trying to cyber attack all over India." Now, the entire nation is on a mission for secretly preparing for a cyber attack. Do not answer the unknown phone calls from anonymous number or click on messages. Another announcement is from KJS Dhillon, "Please do not record any videos or reels and do not share them on social media if you witness any movement of Indian Army, Air Force, or Naval troops or vehicles through your town or city." The reason is that, "You might be unwittingly aiding the enemy." "Any improper use of the internet can aid cybercriminals." Every online error we make can lead to wars on a national or worldwide scale". One of the Indian Army's most crucial initiatives is the implementation of cyber ware and cyber study.

Cybercrime is becoming more prevalent in daily life. Additionally, because India is a developed nation, it faces a high number of cybercrimes [17]. Every hacker is prepared to compromise network devices in India. Thus, this has a significant effect on both the Indian economy and the entire country. Hackers use a variety of illegal tactics to cause users financial harm. However, there is a cyber threat in both domestic and international relations, and hackers have specific plans to carry them out, such as targeting wealthy individuals, businesses, tax payers, and other targets. If a system or network device in India or any organization is compromised, hackers will automatically cause harm to both individuals and our country. This has the biggest effect on the finances of our nation. Thus, enhance both domestic and global cyber security concerns. Additionally, the country's relationships will be managed safely to deter cybercriminals, and everyone will uphold security and protection to build a protective India [33]. Numerous cybercrimes were committed against India's armed forces. The Indian Army is also vulnerable to serious cyber threats. One of the aims of hackers is always to break into our devices in one way or other.

Cyberwar is a possibility The development of cyber terrorists and the use of terrorists as a component of a cyberwar are being observed by other adversary nations [34]. Indian military forces are ready for any kind of conflict, including cyber warfare. However, with today's technology, cybercriminals are prepared to cause unanticipated, dangerous harm. They can maintain a certain distance, but they can also determine the strength and weakness of the military and determine the number of military personnel, weapons, and new missiles. After they send to any online platforms, they reveal our personal information. There is a serious danger watching and monitoring you, so don't

trust any other phone calls, messages, or mail links on the backside. If you know anything about the Indian Army, Navy, Air Force, Police Departments, and other sectors, please don't share it. Please keep safe and secure and refrain from misusing (sharing information on online platforms).

Cyber Security Alert

Cybercrimes are on the rise in tandem with the daily rise in digital usage [35]. Cybercriminals are coming up with new ways to trick the public (Cyber security Alert). Because they are unaware of these crimes, some people are becoming victims of them. Unknowingly, some people are handing over their phones to criminals. This jeopardizes their bank accounts and personal data. Under the aegis of the Indian government, the Indian Cybercrime Coordination Center (I4C) has issued important warnings to the public to exercise caution in this regard. Additionally, it has recommended not to install certain apps in your phones [20].

Don't Use These Apps

The government has advised citizens to remove any installed screen-sharing apps right away and has issued a warning against downloading any new ones [36]. According to some reports, these apps allow criminals to view your phone's screen, giving them access to private data like your bank account information, messages, and one-time passwords. Cyber criminals can empty your bank accounts through these apps. As a result, it is recommended to stop downloading and using these apps altogether.

Be Careful When Granting Permissions

A new app will ask for permissions when it is installed. Without reading them, many people consent to everything. This has also been warned to be extremely dangerous [38]. It has been mentioned that criminals can see everything you do on your phone thanks to screen-sharing apps. For

instance, they are able to view the OTPs you get when you make bank transactions. For this reason, you should be cautious when giving apps permissions [21].

3. GENERAL GUIDELINES

These are some of the general guidelines to be followed for safeguarding ourselves from intentional and unintentional cyber attacks.

Privacy Settings

Cyber security agencies emphasized the importance of social media privacy settings in preventing cybercrime. They advised you to change the settings on your social media accounts in this respect. They advised making sure that not everyone can see your personal information. For instance, you should keep your address, phone number, and pictures private. They emphasized that doing this will make it more difficult for hackers to abuse your data [22].

These Precautions are Mandatory:

Remove screen-sharing apps: Get rid of any apps that are currently on your phone.
Examine permissions carefully: When installing new apps, carefully review the permissions they request.
Privacy on Social Media: Verify that your social media accounts' privacy settings are accurate.
Avoid clicking on dubious links: Avoid clicking on unidentified messages or links.
Update your phone: Update the software on your smart phone on a regular basis.
Taxpayers are the target of cybercriminals. Phishing emails purporting to be IT returns. Phishing emails disguised as IT returns are being sent by certain cyber gangs that prey on income tax payers. People are advised by Cyber Crime ACP Shivamaruti to be on the lookout for these types of scams. It is definitely a scam if you receive an email with a link that purports to be an IT return [26]. Taxpayers are the target of cybercriminals. Phishing

emails purporting to be IT returns: Be wary of online scams using videounibots.com.

City of Hyderabad: Phishing emails disguised as IT returns are being sent by certain cyber gangs that prey on income tax payers. People are advised by Cyber Crime ACP Shivamaruti to be on the lookout for these types of scams. It is unquestionably a scam if you receive an email with a link purporting to be an IT return. They are cautioning against clicking on the link in any situation. They are requesting that they keep in mind that under no circumstances will the authorities send them emails containing links to income tax refunds. Officials are making it clear that IT returns do not require a PIN, password, or other information [27].

Don't Click on E-mails

Income tax payers' information is being gathered by cybercriminals, who then send them emails requesting a refund. They are sending you an email with a link stating that you have received a refund after filing your income taxes and that you must enter the information online in order for the funds to be credited to your account. A phony website that looks like the Income Tax Department website opens if you click on the link labeled "Tax Refund Online Form." They claim that the full amount of the IT return will be deposited into your account within 24 hours if you provide your bank account information, password, and PIN on this page. Cybercriminals are then draining the account after inserting malware through phishing emails and links [31].

Precautions to Take

URL links sent by cybercriminals under the guise of IT returns should not be copied and pasted. Don't send them to other people. Regularly run antivirus software on your computer and phone. Only use the approved website to make IT

payments and returns. Passwords should be changed often. Turn on two-step bank account verification. Notify the cybercrime authorities right away if you receive these emails on a regular basis [39].

Three people are arrested after the CBI busts a cybercrime gang that operates out of apartments in Pune. In raids in Pune and Mumbai, the CBI apprehends a cybercrime syndicate that defrauds Americans and confiscates money, drugs, and incriminating digital evidence. According to officials on Friday, July 25, 2025, the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) has detained three members of a sophisticated cybercrime syndicate that allegedly used VoIP spoofing and phishing calls to defraud foreign nationals, mostly Americans, out of approximately ₹3–4 crore.

The agency raided seven locations in Pune and Mumbai as part of a broad crackdown that started on Thursday, July 24, 2025, and ended on Friday, July 25, 2025. Nine people were detained for running a phony call center that preyed on Americans and Indians. The detectives claimed to have found more than 150 grams of suspected narcotics in addition to digital devices. They claimed that during the bust, ₹1.60 lakh in mysterious cash and incriminating digital evidence from 27 cell phones and 17 laptops were also found. Amit Dube, Tarun Shenai, and Gonsalves Savio were taken into custody by the agency and brought before a special CBI court in Mumbai. The court remanded them to the agency's custody until July 30 so that they could be questioned further about their operations and co-accused [40].

4. MODUS OPERANDI

The term "cyber" is revolutionizing the entire world. Many people are attacked by themselves, causing their own problems, and some people are attacked inadvertently. Numerous papers, such as

those from NASA, ISRO, Air Ways (Air Ports), the Military, industries, medicine, education, and the news, are useful in protecting our devices from hackers. Every area will be secured to protect our departments, but hackers always use a variety of methods to get past the network as a whole. As a result, every paper offers crucial advice for protecting our network. Security is a medication that functions similarly to a firewall and uses updated software to track down hackers. In addition to hackers, they also monitor hacking ideas and methods to quickly detect and protect our networked devices.

Hackers use basic items that may seem simple to you, but they are giving hackers the opportunity to compromise your system. Don't give hackers a chance. Avoid giving hackers a chance by adhering to cyber security protocols, which include identifying our weak points, identifying the types of attacks and threats, and learning about cybercrimes and their purposes. After determining your weaknesses, kindly maintain a high level of security. Maintain security procedures and update your security every two seconds. Cyber security adheres to all directives from our governments and central government security protocols [37]. In addition to governments, news channels on television also offer advice on how to keep our gadgets safe, but you all know it will be risky. Because please abide by all cyber security guidelines and directives from higher authorities.

5. DISCUSSION

Cyber Guardian will be created on future because this cyber guardian looks like a full secured package in our surroundings they will acts like Cyber Wall. Any hacker don't try to hack our devices because our surroundings full secured with a big Cyber wall . so, there is high advantage to future generations.

Trends is going on generation to generation but also every trend is creating a loop hole they give chance to third persons this not giving chance to any other third person. Because there is big weapon is there that is Cyber Wall. So Now developing or creating every new trend will based on automatic Cyber wall protection they will security is very without any loop holes this Cyber Wall will be helpful to not only a single person they also help the entire organizations, institutions, industries, big world organizations, every one individually creates a Cyber wall for Our country boarder areas also after that easily identify where the threat is occurred then solve that easily with detecting hacker creating problem after that maintain the cyber safe shield.

Come of every future New trends will automatically add this cyber Wall they protecting us with safe and securely. So entire future generation will be secured with this Cyber wall Now, everyone without any think happily invite the new trends . Because there is Cyber wall is not only secured our devices or our organizations they will secure entire world.

6. CONCLUSION

Our Prospects every sector of India's development will be highly secured through the use of robust firewalls and cyber security applications. Antivirus software was also used by reliable websites. All contribute to the establishment of the Indian Cyber Safeguard. Cyber wars, cyber attacks, cybercrimes, digital crimes, and other hacking methods are not likely to occur in the future. No hacker can cause problems for our Indian people or our front-line military forces, nor can they burden our motherland, India (All Border Area Forces). The use of Indian Future Trends has made every area secure.

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